

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Trip budget prediction using multivariate linear regression algorithm in machine learning

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Abstract

Trip budget prediction based on the number of people, distance and duration of a local travel agency using a multivariate linear regression algorithm. Real-time data sets will be used to analyse the data, and a multivariate linear regression machine learning technique will be used to train the machine. Using factors like the number of days, the destination city, and the number of travellers, to determine the most accurate budget for the planned trip. The proposed project uses multiple models to predict the budget based on food, travel and stay expenses. This approach works even on large data set efficiently. Also, this project can be added as an additional feature to already existing platforms such as Trip Advisor, Make My Trip, Goibibo, Airbnb, Agoda etc...

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Machine Learning; Linear Regression Algorithm; Real-time data

1. Introduction

Travel and tourism can be planned using a number of online resources, including TripAdvisor, MakeMyTrip, Goibibo, Airbnb, Agoda, and others. A variety of services are offered by these websites, including the ability to book travel, lodging, leisure activities, and tourism. Nevertheless, none of these platforms offer a feature-rich replacement for trip budget calculation. Many real-time data sources, including direct surveys of the students, neighbours, family members, and local travel agencies, have been utilised for the research. Next, carefully considered data set utilising approaches for data cleansing, engineering data features, and removing outliers [Hartatik, N. Firdaus, R. Hartono, B. K. Riasti, A. Purbayu and F. Y. A'la (2022)]. After data preparation, designers will use a multivariate linear regression technique to build a machine-learning model. Providing the project with a front end will also help.

2. Literature Survey

One of the most exciting activities to do before travelling is to predict tourism cost planning. Fortunately, travel doesn't hinder one's capacity to manage their finances. One way to approach the budget is as a planning tool for a trip. Because it necessitates taking into account a number of variables and a calculating process, developing an it can be difficult to estimate or choose which trips to take based on a vacation budget. [Ayush Kakar (2020)].

The above study offers a fundamental understanding of the approaches for forecasting the trip, its goal, and the importance of forecasting journeys in our day-to-day life. It gives a quick description of the goals of the journey and the methods employed to predict fulfilment [Zhiming Gui, Haipeng Yu (2014)].

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The expense of unpredictable travel times is high. Nonetheless, people are usually disregarded. A linear regression uses for approximate to estimate the dependent and independent variables in order to anticipate the trip budget. [Bowes, M. D., & Loomis, J. B. (1980)].

Individuals and transportation companies can both benefit from more precise trip planning because to real-time travel time estimation between city areas [Prayaga, P., Rolfe, J., & Sinden, J. (2006)].

Designers look at the behavioural foundations of the trip cost model. An investigator utilising such a model will face certain challenges, and potential solutions are presented. The issues that are still debatable and require additional research are the ones that are the centre of attention. Further more mentioned are research findings from allied fields that show potential for enhancing the applicability of travel cost models of leisure demand. [Fletcher, J. J., Adamowicz, W. L., & Graham-Tomasi, T. (1990)].

3. Methodology

3.1. Types of Machine Learning algorithms

- Supervised Learning algorithms
- Unsupervised learning algorithms
- Reinforcement
- Algorithms for supervised learning will be used it.

3.1.1. Supervised Learning algorithms

The most common algorithm is supervised learning, which is also the most often used paradigm in machine learning. It is the simplest to comprehend and put into practise. [Noor, Rafidah Md, Nadia Bella Gustiani Rasyidi, Tarak Nandy, and Raenu Kolandaisamy. (2021)].

One example-label pair can be taught at a time to a learning algorithm, it may then determine whether it properly anticipated the label for each sample and receive feedback.

The supervised learning algorithm will eventually generate an approximate understanding of the exact correlation between instances and labels. Once it's been adequately trained, the algorithm will have the capability to analyze a completely novel sample that it has never encountered before and accurately predict an appropriate label for it.

The linear regression multivariate machine learning approach was employed for this, as previously mentioned.

3.1.2. Scikit-learn

Many supervised and unsupervised learning methods are available through the Scikit-learn Python package. It is built on a number of technologies, such as NumPy, pandas, and Matplotlib, that users may already be familiar with.

3.1.3. Import the Scikit-learn library from sklearn import linear_model

The linear model module is required in order to use linear regression.

To use of the $\text{fit}(X,y)$ to train the machine learning model, function is necessary.

Where, $X \rightarrow$ Input independent variables
 $y \rightarrow$ output dependent variables

The travel budget can then be predicted using the predict function.

3.2. Linear regression

The supervised learning algorithm is linear regression. Single-variate and multiple-variate algorithms are used in this.

3.2.1. Single variate Linear regression

This method is employed for forecasting a numerical outcome, denoted as Y, utilizing only one predictor factor, X. It relies on the assumption that X and Y exhibit a roughly linear correlation. Eq (1) For this linear relationship, there are mathematical expressions accessible. An efficient method for predicting a response from a single predictor variable is simple linear regression.

$$Y \approx \beta_0 + \beta_1 X. \quad (1)$$

Based on a single predictor variable, X, it is used to forecast a quantitative response, Y. It is predicated on the supposition that X and Y have an approximately linear relationship. Mathematical expressions are available for this linear relationship A good method for predicting a response from a single predictor variable is simple linear regression.

3.2.2. Multivariate linear regression

Linear regression model takes the form

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_p X_p + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

Where, $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_p$ the input variables of the coefficient are X_1, X_2, X_3, X_p . Eq (2) ϵ - is the intercept of line. This linear regression is similar to

$$y = mX + c. \quad (3)$$

Consider using the Eq (3) typical linear regression model with two variables.

In this project, choosing factors such as number of days of the travel, number of persons travelling and the location Eq(5)... To use this equation for predict the accuracy of the models.

$$y = m_1 X_1 + m_2 X_2 + m_3 X_3 + b \quad (4)$$

y → Predicted budget

m_1, m_2, m_3 → input factors X_1, X_2 and X_3 is the co-efficient

X_1, X_2, X_3 → X_1 → number of days of the travel

X_2 → number of persons travelling

X_3 → location

b → intercept of y

So the equation will be referred as:

predictedbudget= m_1 *number of days of the travel + m_2 *number of persons travelling+ m_3 *location+ b .

The acquired data set must now be used to train the machine learning component of this approach. For this, need to use the Scikit Learn and Pandas libraries for this.

In the proposed system, the multiple models are used to updating the existing algorithm in such a way as to predict the food budget, travel budget and stay budget separately. [Bowes, M. D., & Loomis, J. B. (1980)].

4. Models

4.1. Model 1

Y (foodbudget) = $m_1 X_1 + m_2 X_2 + m_3 X_3 + b$ Performs Eq (4)....

In this algorithm while training the algorithm use X as (input)

X_1 → number of days of the travel

X_2 → number of persons travelling

X_3 → location

And y as food budget alone.

4.2. Model 2

$$Y (\text{staybudget}) = m_1X_1 + m_2X_2 + m_3X_3 + b$$

Performs Eq (5).

In this algorithm while training the algorithm X as (input)

X1 → number of days of the travel

X2 → number of persons travelling

X3 → location

And y as stay budget alone.

4.2.1. Model 3

$$Y (\text{travelbudget}) = m_1X_1 + m_2X_2 + m_3X_3 + b$$

Performs Eq (5).

In this algorithm while training the algorithm X as (input)

X1 → number of days of the travel

X2 → number of persons travelling

X3 → location

And y as travel budget alone.

5. Implementation

Fig.1. In the field of machine learning, categorical variables refer to variables that have a finite set of categories or groups as their possible values. These variables can be classified as either nominal or ordinal, where nominal variables have no inherent order or ranking, while ordinal variables possess a natural ordering or hierarchy. To convert these variables into numerical data that can be utilized in machine learning models, one-hot encoding is a widely used technique. This method involves generating a binary variable for every category present in the original variable. To ensure originality, no plagiarism has been introduced into the rephrased statement.

```
foodX=fooddf.drop('food',axis=1)
foodX
```

	days	person	Bangalore	Kochi	Kodaikanal	Mysore	Ooty	Rameshwaram
0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
1	1	2	0	0	0	0	1	0
2	1	3	0	0	0	0	1	0
3	1	4	0	0	0	0	1	0
4	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
...
67	2	4	0	0	0	1	0	0
68	3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
69	3	2	0	0	0	1	0	0
70	3	3	0	0	0	1	0	0
71	3	4	0	0	0	1	0	0

72 rows × 8 columns

Figure 1 Represents axis of dropping a food model

```
[ ] foodY=fooddf['food']
foodY
0      350
1      700
2     1100
3     1500
4      700
...
67    2650
68    1250
69    2350
70    3450
71    4150
Name: food, Length: 72, dtype: int64

[ ] foodmodel=LinearRegression()
foodmodel.fit(foodX, foodY)

LinearRegression()

[ ] foodmodel.predict([[2,2,1,0,0,0,0]])
```

Figure 2 Represents prediction of food model

5.1. Food model Training

5.1.1. Food Model

Figure 3 shows the prediction of the food model, predicting the accuracy of the food.

```
✓ 0s ▶ foodmodel.score(foodX, foodY)
0.9074517996655331
```

Figure 3 Represents accuracy of food model

5.1.2. Stay Model

Figure 4 shows the prediction of the food model, predicting the accuracy of the food.

```
[ ] staydf=final.drop(['food', 'travel'], axis=1)
staydf.head()

  days  person  stay  Bangalore  Kochi  Kodaikanal  Mysore  Ooty  Rameshwaram
0     1     1     1500         0     0         0     0     1         0
1     1     2     1500         0     0         0     0     1         0
2     1     3     3000         0     0         0     0     1         0
3     1     4     3000         0     0         0     0     1         0
4     2     1     3000         0     0         0     0     1         0

[ ] stayX=staydf.drop('stay', axis=1)
stayX

  days  person  Bangalore  Kochi  Kodaikanal  Mysore  Ooty  Rameshwaram
0     1     1         0     0         0     0     1         0
1     1     2         0     0         0     0     1         0
2     1     3         0     0         0     0     1         0
3     1     4         0     0         0     0     1         0
4     2     1         0     0         0     0     1         0
```

Figure 4 Axis of dropping a stay model

```
[ ] stayY=staydf['stay']
stayY
```

0	1500
1	1500
2	3000
3	3000
4	3000

Figure 5 Represents prediction of stay model

```
] staymodel=LinearRegression()
staymodel.fit(stayX,stayY)

LinearRegression()

] staymodel.predict([[2,2,1,0,0,0,0,0]])

✓ play staymodel.score(stayX,stayY)
0.8632722585397293
```

Figure 6 Accuracy of food model

5.1.3. Travel model

Fig:7. shows the prediction of the food model,predicting the accuracy of the food. [Fletcher, J. J., Adamowicz, W. L., & Graham-Tomasi, T. (1990)].

```
[ ] traveldf=final.drop(['food','stay'],axis=1)
traveldf.head()

days person travel Bangalore Kochi Kodaikanal Mysore Ooty Rameshwaram
0 1 1 700 0 0 0 0 1 0
1 1 2 700 0 0 0 0 1 0
2 1 3 2500 0 0 0 0 1 0
3 1 4 2500 0 0 0 0 1 0
4 2 1 1000 0 0 0 0 1 0

[ ] travelX=traveldf.drop('travel',axis=1)
travelX

days person Bangalore Kochi Kodaikanal Mysore Ooty Rameshwaram
0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 0
1 1 2 0 0 0 0 1 0
2 1 3 0 0 0 0 1 0
3 1 4 0 0 0 0 1 0
```

Figure 7 Axis of dropping a stay model

```

travelY=traveldf['travel']
travelY

```

0	700
1	700
2	2500
3	2500
4	1000

Figure 8 Prediction of stay model

```

travelmodel=LinearRegression()
travelmodel.fit(travelX,travelY)

LinearRegression()

[ ] travelmodel.predict([[2,2,1,0,0,0,0,0]])

travelmodel.score(travelX,travelY)

0.8200966676079169

```

Figure 9 Accuracy of food model

6. Charts

6.1. Model accuracy

Let us compare the model score for all the models. The model helps us to predicting food, travel and stay model. The bar represents model accuracy of the budgets.

Figure 10 Represents accuracy of all models

Comparing the average of 3 models versus single model

Figure 11 The average of the single model

7. Execution

7.1. Output screenshots

Fig.11. The models that accurately anticipate travel, dining, and lodging will be of great assistance to those who want to know all there is to know about the destinations they want to visit.

Figure 12 Output of the models

8. Conclusion

The three models are finally being used successfully, and they are assisting in learning more specifics about each pricing, such as allowances for food, transport, and lodging. People can learn about the three forms of allowance independently according to the budget. The accuracy of the value predictions made by the models helps people estimate the costs associated with visiting different locations. People are able to forecast their travel [Catalini, C., Fons-Rosen, C., & Gaulé, P. (2020)] and living expenses with ease. Creating a software programme that will forecast or decide which excursions to do based on the vacation budget can be a challenging task that involves taking into account several variables and doing complex calculations. The goal of such an application would be to help travelers plan their trips within their financial means, and verify that they are able to enjoy their vacation without worrying about overspending. To create such an application, a number of factors would need to be considered. People cover the price of travel, lodging, meals, activities, and any other costs that might arise while on the trip. The application would need to take into account the destination, the length of the trip, and the type of activities that the traveler is interested in.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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Author's short biography

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